

Conventional and rotational magnetocaloric effect in Gd films

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Received xxxxxx

Accepted for publication xxxxxx

Published xxxxxx

Abstract

Magnetic refrigeration offers a sustainable and emission-free solution to the prevalent heat-pumping systems used worldwide. Typically, it utilizes the magnetocaloric effect (MCE) to achieve cooling by changing the external magnetic field intensity. However, an alternative approach involves maintaining a fixed field intensity while manipulating its orientation to induce temperature changes, in an effect known as the rotating magnetocaloric effect (RMCE). While the RMCE has been extensively studied in materials with magnetocrystalline anisotropy, its investigation in polycrystalline magnetocaloric samples with asymmetric shapes has been lacking until recently. In this case, the RMCE is induced by the demagnetizing effect, which becomes more pronounced in high aspect-ratio sample geometries exhibiting different effective demagnetizing factors at different orientations, such as in films. In this work, we characterize the conventional and rotational MCE of 40 μm -thick gadolinium films through magnetization and direct temperature measurements. The maximum adiabatic temperature change achieved under a 1 T magnetic field was 2.05 K when the film was oriented in plane with the field and 1.25 K when the film was perpendicular to the magnetic field, corresponding to an adiabatic temperature difference of around 0.8 K which may be induced through magnetic field rotation. Additionally, the maximum adiabatic temperature change upon rotation is shown to exhibit a non-monotonous behaviour with field intensity, displaying a peak value for field intensities around 0.8 T. The high aspect ratio of the Gd film has been demonstrated to considerably enhance the intensity of demagnetizing field-based RMCE compared to bulk samples, paving the way for future research in this emerging field of magnetic refrigeration cooling.

Keywords: magnetocaloric effect, rotating magnetocaloric effect, thick film, magnetic refrigeration, demagnetizing field

1. Introduction

While currently indispensable for space cooling and product refrigeration [1], vapor compression refrigeration systems account for over 20% of the overall electricity use worldwide [2] and 10% of the greenhouse gas emissions [3]. Because of this significant and negative environmental impact, research into alternative technologies is critical. Magnetic refrigeration (MR) is one of the most promising alternatives [4, 5, 6], as it relies on solid-state refrigerants, eliminating the need for environmentally harmful/hazardous gases while also allowing for the construction of efficient cooling devices [7, 8, 9]. In MR, the temperature of the active material changes when subjected to a magnetic field change due to the magnetocaloric effect (MCE). Heat flows from the magnetocaloric material to the cold/hot sinks through a thermal exchange fluid. Research in this field has primarily concentrated on bulk magnetocaloric samples in the grams-to-kilograms weight range, typically shaped in plates, spheres, fragments, and powders [10, 11]. However, an ongoing trend towards device miniaturization has spurred additional investigations into magnetocaloric materials with reduced dimensions down to the micro and nanoscale, such as thin films and ribbons [12, 13, 14, 15], with several reports already stressing the general consequences to the magnetic and magnetocaloric properties when scaling down the materials' dimensions [14, 16, 17, 18]. The properties of the magnetocaloric materials have been found to be positively influenced by confinement effects, strain, and a high surface-to-volume ratio [19, 20], making them suitable for micro-device cooling [21, 22, 23] or thermomagnetic energy harvesting [24, 25, 26]. Furthermore, the ability to grow magnetocaloric micro and nanostructures unleashes the potential for cross-coupled effects as those remarkably illustrated by Moya et al. [27].

Gadolinium (Gd) is considered the benchmark material for magnetic cooling systems since it exhibits a strong MCE near room temperature ($T_c \approx 295$ K). Nevertheless, there are several other room temperature magnetocaloric materials that exhibit significant large MCE, such as the following families of alloys $\text{Gd}_5(\text{Si,Ge})_4$, $\text{La}(\text{Fe,Si})_{13}$, MnFePSi , NiMnIn , MnCoGe [8, 9, 10, 14, 28, 29]. The thermomagnetic properties of Gd have been characterized not only in its bulk scale [30] [31] but also down to the microscale, including thick and thin films [32, 33], ribbons [34, 35, 36], microwires [37, 38, 39] and nanoparticles [40, 41, 42]. However, most of the existing data is limited to the isothermal entropy change $\Delta S_{iso}(T, H)$ curves since magnetization measurements are relatively easy to perform with standard commercially available magnetometers, including on very low mass samples.

Direct measurement of the MCE (the adiabatic temperature difference, ΔT_{ad}) in micrometric samples is very challenging due to the rapid thermal diffusion towards the sample-holder

and even to the thermometer itself [43, 44, 45]. Despite this difficulty in ensuring adiabatic conditions, several direct thermometry methods have already been successfully employed to measure magnetocaloric alloy microwires [46, 47] and ribbons [48, 49, 50, 51]. Each home-built setup uses micro-thermocouples with a wire diameter between 25 – 80 μm . Ribbons are usually stacked to increase their thermal mass relative to that of the thermocouple, thus overcoming the difficulties of measuring ΔT_{ad} directly [49, 50]. Alternatively, non-contact thermometry methods have also been successfully used to measure temperature changes of scaled-down samples [52, 53], including Gd thin films and foils [54, 55].

Direct MCE measurements can be further improved by faster magnetic field application, which reduces the time for heat diffusion and thus improves adiabaticity. High pulsed magnetic fields with application rates on the order of 10^3 T s^{-1} have already been used to measure small magnetocaloric bulk samples with great precision and accuracy [56, 57]. While yielding impressive results, this technique with almost perfect adiabatic conditions has never been applied to measure $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H)$ curves for reduced-size samples, such as films.

Apart from the conventional MCE, one can also induce an adiabatic temperature change by changing the orientation of a magnetic field of constant intensity applied to an asymmetrically shaped magnetocaloric sample through the so-called demagnetizing field-based rotating magnetocaloric effect (RMCE) [58, 59]. This phenomenon should be more pronounced in thin films due to their high aspect ratio resulting in extremely different demagnetizing factors along the in-plane and out-of-plane orientations of the magnetic field.

When a ferromagnetic or paramagnetic body is in an external magnetic field, H_{ext} , its magnetic moments tend to align with it. However, the demagnetizing field, H_d , generated by the material's magnetization, M , tends to oppose this external field. The total internal magnetic field, H_{int} , is, therefore, the difference between H_{ext} and H_d , and it is given by [60],

$$H_{int} = H_{ext} - H_d = H_{ext} - DM(H_{int}). \quad (1)$$

Assuming a homogeneous magnetization throughout the body, the effective demagnetizing factor, D , is a position-independent constant that assumes values between 0 and 1 [61]. Infinite sheets (shapes where one dimension is orders of magnitude smaller than the other two dimensions) have $D = 1$ in a direction perpendicular to the plane and $D = 0$ if the magnetic field is in-plane. Thin film samples can be assumed to be infinite sheets. This implies that a 90-degree rotation of a thin film results in a maximum variation of H_{int} . This characteristic makes thin films particularly relevant for demagnetizing field-based RMCE.

Gadolinium thick-film samples hold paramount potential, spanning applications from on-chip cooling to energy harvesting, while also serving as a crucial avenue for investigating the potential of the demagnetizing field-based RMCE. This work aims to fully characterize the MCE of a Gd 40 μm -thick film through temperature and magnetization measurements performed both in-plane and perpendicular to the external magnetic field. The direct temperature measurements are performed in two different setups already used to measure Gd bulk samples [57] [58]. The setup used in [57] allows for almost perfect adiabatic conditions since it operates with pulsed magnetic fields. The second setup [58] enables temperature measurements during rotation of the magnetic field.

2. Experimental Details

The three free-standing Gd thick-film samples used in this work were cut from a single larger Gd film fabricated by triode sputtering onto a Si substrate that was later peeled off as described in detail in [24]. The 40 μm -thick Gd layer is sandwiched between 0.1 μm thick buffer and capping layers of tantalum, resulting in a free-standing Ta/Gd/Ta trilayer. The morphology and crystallographic structure of the film was analyzed by atomic force microscopy (AFM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The respective results are presented in Section 1 of the Supplementary Information and indicate that the Gd film is mainly polycrystalline, although it shows some minor texturization.

The effective demagnetizing factor, D , when required, was determined by calculating the reciprocal of the slope of the magnetization versus external magnetic field curves for lower fields, at low temperatures. The experimental method employed is susceptible to slight deviations from the condition $D_x + D_y + D_z = 1$ due to the inherent uncertainty of the SQUID magnetometer and the assumption that H_{int} is uniformly null across the entire sample, a condition that may not hold for non-elliptical sample geometries.

Sample 1 has a mass of (2.04 ± 0.05) mg, a thickness of 40 μm , and approximately rectangular surface area with 2.2×3.0 mm^2 . The mass contribution of the Ta layers to the total mass of the sample was assumed to be negligible ($\sim 1\%$), as justified in Section 2 of the Supplementary Information. This sample was magnetically characterized in a SQUID magnetometer with the external field parallel and perpendicular to it, which corresponded to the experimentally determined demagnetizing factors of $D_{\parallel} = 0.028$ and $D_{\perp} = 0.999$, respectively. To obtain magnetization curves in the in-plane magnetic field configuration, sample 1 was wrapped with one layer of Teflon tape and fixed to a quartz sample holder with Kapton tape. To obtain magnetization curves in the perpendicular magnetic field configuration, sample 1 was stacked between two quartz rods locked in a brass sample

holder with Kapton tape. Both assemblies are pictured in Fig. S3.

The magnetization measurements were carried out in a commercial MPMS-3 superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer from Quantum Design [62]. For both magnetic field orientations in sample 1, the isothermal magnetization versus field curves and the isofield magnetization versus temperature curves were obtained for fields up to 1 T and in a temperature range of 260-330 K, around the transition temperature of Gd. The absolute magnetization values obtained were adjusted to account for geometric effects associated with the sample shape and mounting, employing a technique outlined previously [63].

Sample 2 consists of two 40 μm thick films, each with an approximately rectangular surface area of 4.6×7.0 mm^2 , stacked together to form a total thickness of 80 μm . This sample was used to perform the direct temperature measurements via a thermocouple in setup A, as later described in this section. The measurements were performed in three distinct ways: by applying the magnetic field parallel to the sample's plane, $H_{ext} \parallel$; by applying the field perpendicular to the sample's plane, $H_{ext} \perp$; and by rotating the magnetic field from perpendicular to parallel to the sample's plane, $H_{ext} \perp \rightarrow H_{ext} \parallel$.

Sample 3 also consists of two thick films stacked together, with a total thickness of 80 μm , and a surface area of 2.2×2.2 mm^2 . This last sample was used to measure temperature directly in setup B, as described later in this section. The measurements were performed both with in-plane ($H_{ext} \parallel$) and perpendicular ($H_{ext} \perp$) magnetic field configurations.

Setup A was used for the direct MCE and RMCE measurements of sample 2. The temperature was measured with a 25 μm -diameter wire type-K thermocouple with the sensing junction glued in between the two 40 μm Gd thick films with GE-varnish, as pictured in Fig. S4(a), (b) and (c). The sample was measured in a vacuum, meaning pressure below 10^{-4} mbar. To apply a magnetic field of 1 T, we used a hollow cylinder-shaped Halbach array consisting of 8 segments of permanent magnets (Fig. S4(d)). To apply magnetic fields up to 0.8 T, we used an electromagnet (Fig. S4(e)). The electromagnet's maximum sweep rate was attainable by manually moving the electromagnet in and out of the cryostat tip (to predetermined and measured positions), where the sample is located. The magnetic field sweep rate impact on the samples' temperature can be seen in Section 5 of the Supplementary Information. Manual application, removal and rotation of the magnetic field with the Halbach magnet took less than one second, corresponding to a sweep rate of approximately 1 T s^{-1} . Application and removal of the magnetic field of the electromagnet, performed by manually dragging it, also took less than one second, while rotating the magnetic field with this device took between one and two

seconds. The characteristic time for temperature relaxation is approximately twenty seconds (see Fig. S5 and Fig. S6) meaning that it is ten to twenty times longer than the time required to move the magnetic field source in and out of the cryostat tip. For each set of measurements, the magnetic field underwent some mechanical motion (i.e. applied, removed, or rotated) five times at each stabilized T_i temperature. Following each movement, we allowed a 25-second interval for the sample's temperature to relax before initiating the subsequent measurement. This protocol is graphically exemplified in Fig. S6 for $T_i \approx 297$ K for repeated application and removal of a magnetic field of 1 T.

Setup B was used to test the magnetocaloric effect directly in sample 3 for in-plane and perpendicular field orientations (Fig. S7). The measurements were conducted at the Dresden High Magnetic Field Laboratory (HLD-EMFL). We utilized pulsed magnetic fields with a maximum amplitude of 10 T and a total pulse duration of 130 ms, thereby the field change rate is sufficiently fast for the measurements to be considered adiabatic. The temperature change was measured using a 25 μm thick type E thermocouple, with a fast enough response and low thermal mass. A detailed description of the measurement setup and pulse field measurement capabilities is provided in [57]. For the measurements, we prepared sample 3 by directly welding one end of the thermocouple between the two pieces of the Gd film, glued with silver epoxy on the edge. Additionally, to ensure adiabatic conditions, the sample was measured in a vacuum of 10^{-5} mbar. Furthermore, the sample was placed on a frame to decouple it thermally and prevent heat transfer to the sample holder.

In setup A, despite the fact that the thermal relaxation occurs in a larger ($\sim 20\times$) time frame than the field application, it is clear that the thermal contact of the GE varnish with the sample resulted in an underestimation of ΔT_{ad} . Moreover, in setup A, the sample's surface is glued to a piece of paper to secure it to the cryostat (see Fig. S4(c)). In setup B, however, the thermocouple tip is welded directly onto the film (see Fig. S7(a)). Furthermore, the use of pulsed fields

ensures that the temperature response of the thermocouple is related to the film's temperature, despite the low amount of thermal paste used to maintain the two halves of the sample together. Additionally, in setup B, the sample is secured in place with GE-varnish, only in contact with the sample holder via a "U" shaped step (see Fig. S7 (b)).

3. Results and Discussion

The temperature-dependent magnetization versus external field curves are represented in Fig. 1(a) for sample 1 measured in-plane ($H_{ext} \parallel$ in blue-green colour palette) and perpendicular ($H_{ext} \perp$ in pink-yellow colour palette) to the external field. The isothermal external magnetic field-dependent magnetization versus field curves are represented in Fig.1(b) for both field orientations in the 260 – 330 K temperature range. The differences in curve profiles for $H_{ext} \parallel$ and $H_{ext} \perp$ are attributed to the demagnetizing effect. These differences are particularly significant at low temperatures when magnetization is at its highest and at low fields when the external magnetic field, H_{ext} , and the demagnetizing field, H_d , are comparable. As expected from equation (1), the magnetization depends on the sample's relative orientation to the external field. Correcting the curves for demagnetization, one can obtain the magnetization as a function of the internal magnetic field, $M(H_{int})$. The $M(H_{int})$ curves obtained for both configurations ideally would collapse, since no intrinsic anisotropy of the material is expected, but some experimental error and non-considered inhomogeneities in the demagnetizing effect results in slight differences, as can be observed in Fig. S8(a) and (b). The $M(H_{ext})$ and $M(H_{int})$ curves for $T = 30$ K are plotted in Fig. S9 for sample 1 in both field orientations and for a Gd bulk sample in-plane with the magnetic field orientation.

Considering the isothermal magnetization versus field curves, one can obtain the isothermal entropy change for a field variation of $-H^i + H^f$ by solving the following equation:

Figure 1. (a) Magnetization vs temperature curves of sample 1 measured in-plane with H_{ext} (blue to green curves) and perpendicular to H_{ext} (pink to yellow curves) for different 0.1 T incremental magnetic fields up to 1 T. (b) Magnetization vs H_{ext} curves of sample 1 measured with both field orientations ($H_{ext} \parallel$ and $H_{ext} \perp$) at different temperatures ranging between 260 and 330 K.

$$\Delta S_{iso}(T, H^f, H^i) = \mu_0 \int_{H^i}^{H^f} \left(\frac{\partial M(T, H)}{\partial T} \right) dH. \quad (2)$$

The $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ curves represented in Fig. 2(a) were obtained through the $M(H_{ext} \parallel)$ data. In comparison with the bulk curve for the same $H_{ext} = 1$ T, the $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ curve for sample 1 has a deviation of -5.5% of the peak amplitude, -0.2% of the maximizing temperature, and 4.3% of the FWHM. These small deviations suggest that the thick film closely matches the behavior of the bulk material.

The isothermal entropy change upon field rotation is also obtained through eq. (2) by considering the internal fields H^i and H^f in each orientation which correspond to the same external field, so that:

$$\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T) = \Delta S_{iso}(T, H_{int} \parallel, 0) - \Delta S_{iso}(T, H_{int} \perp, 0) \quad (3)$$

as shown in [58]. The obtained $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ curves for different H_{ext} intensities are represented in Fig. 2(b). In comparison with the bulk sample, which has a volume of $1.2 \times 1.0 \times 5.0 \text{ mm}^3$, the $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ curve for sample 1 under $H_{ext} = 1$ T has a deviation of 23.9% of the peak amplitude and 1.1% of the maximizing temperature.

While the $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ peak value increases with the magnetic field intensity, the $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ approaches its saturated value at relatively low fields. For a magnetic field of 0.8 T, the maximum value of $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ surpasses slightly the value obtained for 1 T, which emphasizes the non-proportional field dependency. For a magnetic field of 0.6 T, the maximum $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ corresponds to 94% of the maximum value obtained under a 1 T field. This highlights the presence of an optimal region at low fields where the RMCE demonstrates its most impressive performance. In a RMCE-based prototype, the use

of lower fields is especially compelling from an application point-of-view, as it entails a substantial decrease in the permanent magnet material required in the refrigeration device, as previously noted in [58].

The direct temperature measurements performed in sample 2 with the experimental setup A and by applying 1 T are represented in Fig. 3(a). The obtained $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ curve measured under field rotation in setup A (green curve in Fig. 3(a)) exhibits a maximum peak value of 0.7 K at 280 K and a broadening profile as compared to the curves of the conventional MCE. Its ΔT_{ad} values are more significant than the ones obtained for $H_{ext} \perp$ for temperatures lower than 287 K and agree with the ones obtained for $H_{ext} \parallel$ for temperatures lower than 260 K.

The ΔT_{ad} values obtained with setup A for $H_{ext} \parallel$ and $H_{ext} \perp$ are underestimated compared to the ones measured with setup B for the same field intensity, represented in Fig. 3(b). The $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \parallel)$ and $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \perp)$ curves obtained with setup A were within -31.4% and -25.4% of the peak amplitude relative to the curves obtained with setup B, respectively. These discrepant values are expected and are related to setup A's poorer experimental adiabatic conditions relative to setup B, as previously described in the end of last section.

As expected, using both setups, the conventional MCE is maximum when the applied magnetic field is in-plane, due to its lower demagnetizing factor in this configuration. When the applied field is perpendicular to the film, there is a clear and expected reduction of the $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ values measured, particularly in the ferromagnetic region, where the larger magnetization results in an increased demagnetizing effect (eq. (1)). If the internal magnetic field was considered, the $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ values should be field orientation-independent and both $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{int} \parallel)$ and $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{int} \perp)$ curves should be similar to each other, as demonstrated in Section 10 of the Supplementary Information.

The RMCE curves can also be obtained numerically by:

$$\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T + \Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{int} \perp, 0)) = \Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{int} \parallel, 0) - \Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{int} \perp, 0) \quad (4)$$

as demonstrated in detail in [58]. In practice, this corresponds to the difference between the conventional MCE in each H_{ext} orientation with a shift of the initial temperature of $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{int} \perp, 0)$. The obtained curve, represented in Fig. 3(a) in red, appears lower than the one measured directly under field rotation, particularly around T_c , where a larger MCE increases heat exchange rates, as per Fourier's law. In fact, smaller MCE values lead to smaller deviations in the peak amplitude ΔT_{ad} values when compared with measurements on setup B. The absolute values of $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \perp)$ are smaller, resulting in a smaller deviation of $|-25.4\%$ relative to setup B. In contrast, the $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \parallel)$ curve, with larger absolute values, exhibits a larger deviation of $|-31.4\%$ relative to setup B. This discrepancy arises from the deterioration of the experimental adiabatic conditions in setup A as the MCE increases.

The $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ curves obtained in setup A for H_{ext} parallel and perpendicular to the film, under field rotation and by applying equation (4) are represented in Section 11 of the Supplementary Information for different field intensity values (0.2, 0.4, 0.6 and 0.8 T). Similar $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ curves are also plotted for magnetic fields up to 10 T in setup B in Section 12 of the Supplementary Information. Applying equation (4) to the conventional MCE curves measured in both field orientations with setup B, one obtained the curves represented in Fig. S14. The smoother version of these curves is shown in Fig. 4(a). The peak amplitude of the $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T)$ curves tends to stabilize around 1.08 K in the magnetic field region between 0.7 T and 2 T, as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). This non-proportional field dependency of the peak values is similar to the one observed for $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ in Fig. 2(a). The slight fluctuations

Figure 4. (a) RMCE curves obtained by applying equation (4) to the conventional MCE curves obtained with setup B. (b) Peak amplitude and FWHM of the RMCE curves represented in (a) as a function of external magnetic field.

observed between peak amplitudes in this field region can be attributed to the measurement uncertainty of the setup. For a magnetic field of 0.6 T, the peak amplitude corresponds to 94% of the maximum averaged obtained value, similar to the behavior of the $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ curve. Additionally, one can affirm that the peak amplitude gradually decreases for magnetic fields larger than the ones represented here (see Fig. S15). Moreover, increasing the magnetic field intensity results in a corresponding increase in the FWHM of the $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T)$ curves, as represented in Fig. 4(b). Nevertheless, this increase becomes less pronounced for higher magnetic field intensities.

In order to evaluate the suitability of the Gd film to incorporate in refrigeration cycles, let us infer about the amount of heat that will be transfer from the cold to the hot reservoirs through the refrigerant capacity $RC = \int_{T_{cold}}^{T_{hot}} \Delta S_{iso}(T) dT$. The obtained results for RC for the conventional and rotational $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ curves are represented in Figure 5(a) for $T_{cold} = T_C - 15$ K and $T_{hot} = T_C + 15$ K. Similar to the previously observed behavior of the $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ and $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ peak curves, the response of the RC to increasing magnetic field strength is linear for the conventional MCE and plateaus around ≈ 30 J Kg⁻¹ for the RMCE. Moreover, the RC_{RMCE} is of the same order of magnitude as the RC_{MCE} for magnetic fields below 0.6 T, suggesting that a RMCE-based refrigeration device can compete with conventional ones in the low magnetic field region.

To assess the magnitude of the MCE and RMCE of the Gd film in a certain temperature range of use, ΔT , the temperature averaged entropy change (TEC) was calculated as follows:

$$TEC(\Delta T) = \frac{1}{\Delta T} \max \left\{ \int_{T_{mid}-\frac{\Delta T}{2}}^{T_{mid}+\frac{\Delta T}{2}} \Delta S(T)_{\Delta H, T} dT \right\} \quad (5)$$

where T_{mid} is the temperature that maximizes $TEC(\Delta T)$. $TEC(3)$ and $TEC(10)$ were calculated for $\Delta T = 3$ K and 10 K, respectively, and compared with $|\Delta S_{iso}^{max}|$, as shown in Figure 5(b), for both MCE and RMCE entropy change measurements. In both conventional and rotational effects, the obtained $TEC(3)$ values closely match the corresponding $|\Delta S_{iso}^{max}|$ values. It is clear that TEC_{RMCE} is significantly lower than TEC_{MCE} for magnetic fields above 0.6 T, with TEC_{MCE} increasing linearly and TEC_{RMCE} saturating. Nevertheless, TEC_{RMCE} is competitive with TEC_{MCE} in the low-field region (below 0.6 T), while holding the potential to enable simpler, cheaper, more compact and more energy efficient devices.

To compare the curve profile of the $\Delta T_{ad}(T)$ curves from Fig. 3 with the curves obtained for a bulk Gd sample in [58], one normalized and plotted them in Fig. S16 together with the numerically simulated data for a spin 7/2 hexagonal close-packed (HCP) Ising lattice for an infinite sheet. There is very good agreement between the curves obtained for the thick film with both setups, bulk, and simulations.

With the direct $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T)$ and $\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \parallel)$ measurements obtained with setup A, one can compare the performance of the RMCE between bulk and film samples. When plotting $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T) / \Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \parallel)$, it becomes evident that the ratio between the RMCE and the conventional MCE is greater for the film when compared to the bulk sample, as one can see in Fig. 6 (the curve $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T) /$

Figure 5. (a) Refrigerant capacity as a function of magnetic field intensity, obtained by integrating the conventional $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ curve measured in-plane (blue curve) and perpendicular (orange curve) to the magnetic field and by integrating the rotational $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ curve (green curve) from $T_{cold} = T_C - 15$ K to $T_{hot} = T_C + 15$ K. For the sake of clarity, the error bars have not been included, but the relative error is estimated to be less than 5% for all of the data presented. (b) $|\Delta S_{iso}^{max}|$ and TEC as a function of the external magnetic field for MCE (blue and orange curves) and RMCE (green curves) measurements.

$\Delta T_{ad}(T, H_{ext} \perp)$ is plotted in Fig. S17). These experimental observations are in agreement with theoretical predictions, given that the geometry of the film and, consequently, its demagnetizing factor exert a more substantial influence on the demagnetizing field-based RMCE.

4. Conclusion

Our study aimed to investigate the conventional and rotational magnetocaloric properties of 40 μm -thick Gd films in detail. We employed two different setups to measure the conventional MCE directly. As expected, both direct temperature measurement setups resulted in qualitatively identical behaviors of the studied films. Setup A allowed for measurements under field rotation, which were not possible in setup B. Nonetheless, setup B resulted in significantly higher absolute values of the adiabatic temperature change, highlighting the very important role of the experimental method in direct measurements of the magnetocaloric effect, especially in samples with a small mass such as films.

The maximum adiabatic temperature differences for a 1 T field were 2.05 K and 1.25 K for in-plane ($H_{ext} \parallel$) and perpendicular ($H_{ext} \perp$) orientations, respectively, corresponding to a rotational effect of 0.8 K.

The $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ and $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T)$ curves show a region at low fields around 0.7 T and 1.0 T, from which the peak amplitude of both $\Delta S_{iso}^{rot}(T)$ and $\Delta T_{ad}^{rot}(T)$ curves tends to stabilize. This is the magnetic field region where the RMCE demonstrates its greatest utility. The fact that RMCE reaches its peak value at relatively low fields implies that a low volume/mass permanent magnet will be required for RMCE-based refrigeration devices.

The geometry of thick films was confirmed to have improved the efficiency of the demagnetizing field-based RMCE, paving the way for future research in this newly discovered variant of magnetocaloric cooling.

Acknowledgements

The work carried out at Universidade do Porto was developed within the scope of the following projects financed by EEA grants via the project FBR_OC1_85 and by national funds through the FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC), UIDB/04968/2020, UIDP/04968/2020, PTDC/EMETED/3099/2020 (IFIMUP), and LISBOA-01-0247-FEDER-039985/POCI-01-0247-FEDER-039985. The work carried out at Universidade de Aveiro was developed within the scope of the project CICECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials, UIDB/50011/2020, UIDP/50011/2020 & LA/P/0006/2020, financed by national funds through the FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC). The fabrication of Gd thick films was developed during the "HiPerTher-Mag" project (ANR-18-CE05-0019) financed by the French National Research Agency. J. H. Belo

Figure 6. Ratio between the 1 T magnetic field RMCE and the conventional in-plane MCE, from both simulated data and direct measurements obtained with setup A for sample 2 and the bulk sample [58]. The ratio is higher for the film than for the bulk, as expected.

also thanks FCT for the projects PTDC/FISMAL/31302/2017 and CERN/FISTEC/0003/2019 and FCT for his contract DL57/2016, with reference SFRH-BPD-87430/2012, and DL57/2016/CP1454/CT0013, with reference 10.54499/DL57/2016/CP1454/CT0013, DOI: 10.54499/DL57/2016/CP1454/CT0013. R. Almeida acknowledges FCT for the PhD grant with reference 2022.13354.BD.

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